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Relationship Between Teachers' Self- Efficacy and Teachers' Emotions at Secondary Level

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between self-efficacy of teachers and their emotional states in secondary schools in Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJ&K). Using a quantitative approach, the research examines how teachers' belief in their ability to perform job-related tasks influences emotional experiences such as stress, enthusiasm, and burnout. Data collected from secondary school teachers using validated instruments revealed a positive correlation between high self-efficacy and positive emotional outcomes, including increased enthusiasm and reduced levels of stress and burnout which is also statistically significant. Conversely, low self-efficacy was associated with greater emotional distress and job dissatisfaction. The study concludes that improving teacher self-efficacy is crucial for fostering emotional well-being and enhancing overall job performance.

Keywords: *Teacher Self-Efficacy, Emotional States, Stress, Burnout, Enthusiasm, Professional Development, Supportive Environment, Secondary Schools, Mirpur, AJ&K.*

INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy is essentially a belief in one's ability to shape and implement the necessary arrangements to achieve a desired results (Bandura, 1997, p. 3). This concept, first introduced by Albert Bandura in his social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986), emphasizes that an person's performance is influenced by the interplay between personal characteristics (such as beliefs), conduct, and environmental conditions. According to Marsh et al. (2018), self-efficacy is forward-looking, asking questions such as "What can I accomplish?" or "What can I do?" On the other hand, self- concept looks backward, reflecting on past accomplishments. Self-efficacy is future- oriented and tied to expected achievements, while self-concept is influenced by how past accomplishments align with societal norms. Consequently, self-efficacy evaluations are descriptive, while self-concept evaluations are both descriptive and evaluative (Marsh et al., 2018).

In the context of Bandura's concept, "teacher self-efficacy" refers to a teacher's self-assurance in their own ability to enhance student engagement and learning, not only the self-motivated

but with the less motivated students. Teachers efficacy at a holistic level aid in comprehending the effects of faculty traits on student outcomes, whereas, individual teacher's self-efficacy explains how a teachers views are related to students' academic journey. Thus, researching strategies for boosting teachers self efficacy are detrimental to the educational setting. When looking into the effects of teacher beliefs in their abilities, it is important to understand that teachers' belief in self vary from task to tasks, realms and domains. This means that teachers can have very different beliefs about their abilities in various areas. For example, teacher consider themselves very confident in managing a classroom but only feel somewhat uncertain about engaging students in learning. Lastly, teachers' self-efficacy beliefs can change. They can be improved through educational interventions and external support provided in schools (Warner & French, 2019).

The role of teachers goes beyond simple instruction. It includes emotional competence, which is key for managing their own feelings and understanding the emotions of others, particularly in preschool settings positive emotional states help create a more harmonious and supportive learning environment. However, teachers today struggle to connect with varied student personalities. This challenge is made worse by changing responsibilities, expectations, and educational trends. This shifting landscape highlights the need for ongoing growth in preschool education. It also shows the importance of having quality teachers who can inspire and motivate their students (Mujis and Harris, 2007),.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the educational context of Mirpur AJK, understanding the dynamics of teacher self-efficacy and the emotional experiences of secondary school teachers, is crucial for enhancing educational outcomes and teacher well-being. Despite its importance, there is a lack of comprehensive data on the scale of self-efficacy among secondary school teachers with respect to their emotional experiences. There is a gap in understanding how teacher self-efficacy correlates with their emotional states. Therefore, this study has been carried out to fulfill this gap.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To measure the degree of teachers' self-efficacy at secondary schools in Mirpur AJ&K
2. To examine the level of different emotions as experienced by the secondary school's teachers.
3. To investigate the correlation between teachers' self-efficacy and teachers emotional states

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

There is no relation between teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' emotions at secondary schools.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Teachers' self -awareness about their self-efficacy and emotional well-being contribute to a more supportive and motivating atmosphere that can inspire students to perform better academically and emotionally. Understanding how self-efficacy and emotions can help identify levels of emotions to improve teachers' emotional well-being. Building a culture of collaboration among teachers, where they can share experiences and provide emotional support, to enhance self-efficacy across the teaching community.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The subjective assessment that one can successfully finish a task based on one's talents even in difficult situations is known as positive self-perception. Considering the significance of the concept, it is essential to comprehend the process by which teachers develop views about their own efficacy preparation courses. One source of information from which conclusions are drawn

regarding a person's capacity to handle demands and duties of a similar nature in the future is their physiological and emotional states, for instance.

The concept of self-efficacy has been the subject of numerous recent research on teachers' beliefs about teacher education or about working in the field. Few of these, nevertheless, are longitudinal studies that concentrate on how self-efficacy develops both during and after teacher preparation, it was found that significant shifts in student- Self- efficacy in educators develops early in their education and that self-efficacy also rises as teacher training comes to a finish). It is undeniable that teacher education presents a chance; the question is whether or not to take use of it quickly. Nevertheless, following this, teachers' self-efficacy is not completely stable. It is susceptible to modification even later in their career with professional development programs and interventions (Palmer& Noltemeyer, 2019).

Takahashi (2011) presents a socio-cultural perspective that challenges the socio- cognitive theory, which emphasizes individual processing, and instead uses the framework of "communities of practice" to increase teachers' self-efficacy. Teachers are able to co-construct their efficacy beliefs in shared practices, according to his study conducted through interviews with four teachers.

Teacher self-efficacy has a substantial part in goal setting, pursuit and motivation, effort, and resilience in the face of challenges related to a professional career. (Malone, 2006). A school's total capacity is assessed by its perceived collective efficacy, which goes beyond the sum of its members' individual efficacy opinions. It is a thorough examination that considers the group's interaction and collaborative dynamics. (Elliot, 2022). Therefore, it is crucial to look at teachers' collective-efficacy beliefs in order to comprehend teachers and school functions well. Empirical evidence from a variety of contexts, including socio-police, the workplace, and education, supports self-efficacy by showing that higher perceived collective efficacy. (Donohoo, 2020).

In recent years, emotions have come to be recognized as crucial aspects of a teacher's profession. Many contextual factors, such as parent expectations, collegial relationships, principal support, educational regulations, instructors themselves, and their instruction, have an impact on teachers' moods. (Chen.et al., 2020). While instructing and interacting with students, teachers frequently feel a wide range of discrete emotions, including happiness, pride, joy, Anger, tiredness, hopelessness, worry, embarrassment, or boredom. Numerous scenarios and occurrences in the classroom can elicit these feelings. Teachers may become enraged, for example, if pupils disrespect other students or break classroom regulations (Burićn & Frenzel 2019).

On the other hand, educators who see that when the content is taught using a novel approach, pupils advance and become very interested in learning, may conclude that their objective has been realized and thereafter find pleasure in their work. Ultimately, the model posits that the emotions that arise from these cognitive evaluations influence various facets of teachers' instructional conduct, including classroom management, social support, and cognitive and motivational stimulation (Chang et al., 2022). Being a teacher is an extremely difficult job that calls for emotional labor. Given that educators usually have to handle multiple emotional situations at once in the classroom. Throughout the teaching and learning process, the instructor skillfully handles disruptive conduct, fosters a vibrant classroom environment, and offers students emotional support.

More precisely, self-efficacy beliefs determine an individual's capacity to regulate and control their emotions as well as how well they respond to external demands (Biggs et al. ,2017). Individuals who have strong self-efficacy beliefs make better use of their personal resources, set higher goals, and have more optimistic expectations. They also solve problems effectively

and are better able to handle pressures in their lives. Conversely, those with poor self-efficacy views are more likely to doubt their own skills and believe they are unable to handle the demands and challenges in their environment. Negative emotional states such as despair, worry, or powerlessness may arise from this (Schwarzer & Hallum, 2008).

The current study set out to investigate the directionality of the assumed relationship between TSE and the feelings that educators feel when instructing and engaging with students in order to evaluate this hypothesis. Studies that have already been conducted evaluate teachers' affective states in a somewhat wide way, characterizing them as either as a broader effect. As a result, they have overlooked the variety and depth of instructors' unique emotions.

Theoretical Framework

Social cognitive theory applied to the domain of emotions and self-efficacy explains how teachers actively engage with pupils in the classroom to support learning, manage professional challenges, and manage a range of emotions, both positive and negative (e.g., proud, tired, angry, motivated, satisfied, etc.). When social cognitive theory is applied to the domain of self-efficacy and emotions, it can be seen that teachers actively engage with their students in order to support their learning, manage professional challenges, perform well as teachers, and manage a range of emotions, both positive and negative (e.g., pride, tiredness, anger, motivation, satisfaction, etc.). Because both students and teachers are active actors in their surroundings, social cognitive theory also explains how students are influenced by their teachers and teachers are influenced by their pupils. Throughout the entire teaching and learning process, they interacted socially with one another.

Students are influenced by their teachers in two ways: first, they take an interest in their studies and develop positive personal qualities; second, teachers are influenced by their students in that they adapt their teaching strategies to their students' abilities and use various teaching modalities based on the students' learning objectives.

METHODOLOGY

This study's primary objective is to elucidate the connection between Mirpur high school teachers' emotions and self-efficacy. A description and measurement were made of the level of association between two or more variables or sets of scores. in correlational study design using the correlational statistical test. Instead of attempting to control and modify the variables in this approach, the researchers link the data using the correlational statistic (Creswell, 2012). The Study was delimited to the Secondary school teachers in Mirpur AJ&K. The study included all the teachers of Secondary schools of Mirpur City, who are actively employed there and have firsthand experience with emotional and self-efficacious activities. A universal sampling design

was used to choose the participants; this type of design is used to sample a certain population. The two education-related field specialists assessed the research instrument's validity. The instrument statements were corrected in the areas that were found. A pilot study was carried out to evaluate the instrument's dependability. The Cronbach Alpha value was .813 for Teachers Self-Efficacy and .737 for teachers' emotions indicating that the tool is dependable

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teachers Self Efficacy

The mean value of 4.59 for the statement "teachers help their students to think critically"

Sr. No.	Statement	Mean
1	I help my students to think critically.	4.30
2	I can deal with the problematic behavior of some students in classroom.	4.51
3	Exerting a positive influence on my students makes me happy.	4.40
4	I improve the level of understanding of students	4.20
5	I introduce activities in classrooms for enhancing student's creativity.	4.30
6	I control disruptive behavior in classroom easily.	3.8
7	I teach the students according to their mental capabilities	4.2
8	I teach the students according to their mental capabilities	3.7

indicates a high level of agreement among teachers. The mean value of 4.41 for the statement "teachers assess the students' comprehension of what they have taught" indicates a strong level of agreement among teachers. The mean value of 3.81 for the statement "I control disruptive behavior in classroom easily" indicates a moderate to high level of agreement. The mean value of 3.69 for the statement "teachers make their students follow classroom rules" indicates a moderate level of agreement.

Teachers Emotions

Sr. No	Statement	Mean
1	I feel glad when I achieve my teaching goals.	4.40
2	I enjoy when the class atmosphere is positive.	4.41
3	Exerting a positive influence on my students makes me happy.	4.40
4	I feel angry at negative reactions of some students.	3.78
5	The frustration I feel while working with less motivated students undermines my job motivation.	3.8
6	I feel drained, when I complete my work.	3.68
7	I feel hopeless when I think about the bad performance of some students.	3.9
8	I just want to rest at the end of my working day.	4.1368

The finding from the statement "teachers feel content when students understand the material with mean value of 4.51 suggests that, on average, teachers experience a high level of satisfaction. The finding for the statement "They are content when they have a beneficial impact on their students. "With mean value of 4.40 indicates that teachers generally agree with this sentiment. The mean value of 3.93 for the statement "teachers feel hopeless when they think about the bad performance of some students" indicates a moderate level of agreement. The mean value of 3.86 for the statement "teachers provide alternative explanations when students are confused" indicates a moderate to strong level of agreement.

Correlation Analysis

Correlations			
		Emotions	Self-Efficacy
Emotions	Pearson Correlation	1	-.002
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.983
	N	105	105
Efficacy	Pearson Correlation	-.002	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.983	
	N	105	105

The findings shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient between "emotions" and "efficacy" is -0.002, with a significance level of 0.983. This indicates a negligible negative correlation and suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between these two variables.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that teachers are highly committed to helping their students develop critical thinking skills, as evidenced by the high mean score. Moreover, teachers are successfully assessing their students' understanding of the material. This indicates a strong focus on evaluation to device the effectiveness of their teaching methods. It has also been concluded that teachers have a relatively positive view of their ability to manage students behavior. Teachers also agree that they are able to make students follow rules. Teachers feel a high level of satisfaction when students understand the material. Additionally, teachers generally agree that they are content when they have a positive impact on their students. Teachers may experience frustration or disappointment regarding underperforming students. Teachers provide alternative explanations when students are confused. Lastly, there is no statistically significant relationship between the two variables of self- efficacy and emotions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the conclusions the following is recommended, administration may facilitate teachers to enhance self-efficacy to foster a positive learning environment, provide regular feedback, recognize achievements, and encourage collaboration. Workshops may be organized to help teachers to manage emotional well-being more effectively and reduce feelings of frustration. Continuous professional development, may promote collaborative teaching, offer emotional support, encourage positive reinforcement, and engage parents. Further research may be conducted at different level of education with same variables.

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